

Antibacterial studies : The study indicates that all the complexes possess antibacterial activity both for gram-positive and gram-negative organisms. The copper(II) complexes were more active than the other transition metal complexes (Table 1). Differences in antibacterial activity^{1,2} of the ligands and metal complexes may be due to increase in the liposoluble nature of the ligands or the metal in the form of the metal complexes in comparison to the free metal ion or the free ligand.

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Transition Metal Complexes of Nicotinoylaminoguanidine

LALLAN MISHRA*, D. S. KUSHWAHA and V. K. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

and

V. J. RAM^a, V. P. TIWARI^b and L. B. TIWARI^c

^a Medicinal Chemistry Division, CDRI, Lucknow,
^b Ceramic Engineering, I.T. B. H. U., Varanasi, ^c Department of Physics, S.C.P.G. College, Ballia

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THE pharmacological importance of guanidines and substituted guanidines are well-documented¹.

Recently, guanidine derivatives have been reported to possess various biological activities². Isonicotinoylaminoguanidine has been found to show algicidal activity³. The guanidines possess potent donor sites which may be exploited for the complex formation. Thus it was thought worthwhile to investigate the complexing behaviour of similar guanidines, viz. nicotinoylaminoguanidine(L).

Experimental

All of the chemicals used were chemically pure or of AnalaR grade. Solvents were distilled before use.

Preparation of nicotinoylaminoguanidine : It was prepared by the reaction of nicotinic acid hydrazide and S-methylisothiourea sulphate in aqueous NaOH solution using literature procedure⁴ and was crystallised from water, m.p. 260–62° (Table 1).

Preparation of metal complexes : A general procedure was adopted for the formation of the complexes in which the ligand (0.90 g, 0.005 mol) in EtOH (30 cm³) and the metal chloride (0.005 mol, EtOH, 30 cm³) were mixed and stirred for 0.5 h to yield coloured precipitates. The whole mass was then digested on a water-bath for 15 min, cooled, filtered and washed several times with EtOH and dried in hot air oven (< 100°).

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were analysed by the microanalytical method. Metals were estimated gravimetrically⁵ after decomposing the complexes with HNO₃ and HCl. Chloride was estimated as AgCl. Results of elemental analyses are presented in Table 1.

Ir and uv spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and Cary 14 spectrophotometer respectively. Magnetic measurements of the complexes were performed on a Cahn-Faraday electrobalance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as a calibrant and diamagnetic correction was made using Pascal's constants⁶. The photoacoustic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a single beam photoacoustic spectrometer in 400–750 nm region using a tungsten-halogen lamp (600 W) coupled with a 0.25 meter CEL grating monochromator as tunable light source. ESR spectra in solid state (Cu^{II} complex) was recorded on a Varian E4 X-band spectrometer using Coppinger's radical as a marker. TG and DTA were obtained on a Netzsch Simultaneous Thermal Analyser STA 409 in the atmospheric air at a heating rate of 5 K/min. Due to insolubility of the complexes, molar conductance could not be determined.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) suggest the empirical compositions ML_{3/2}Cl₂ (M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}). All the complexes were found to have high m.p. (> 300°).

Ir spectra : Ir spectra of the free ligand showed three medium bands at 3 450, 3 340 and 3 120 cm⁻¹ which were assigned to ν_{NH} vibrations. On complexation, these bands remained unaltered in position and intensity except for the Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes in which the ν_{NH} band was reduced very much in intensity only. The ligand peak observed at 1 660 cm⁻¹ was lowered by ~ 20 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes which indicated the participation of C=O group in coordination to the metal ions. Furthermore, the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)					TG % Loss Found/ (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	10 Dq cm ⁻¹	B' cm ⁻¹	β
		M	C	H	N	Cl					
L(C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ O)		—	46.51 (46.91)	5.28 (5.03)	38.85 (39.12)	—					
MnL _{1.2} Cl ₂	Yellowish green	13.5 (13.9)	32.0 (31.9)	3.0 (3.4)	26.5 (26.6)	17.5 (18.0)	67.8 (68.0)	5.9	6 787	617	0.64
FeL _{1.2} Cl ₂	Dark brown	13.8 (14.1)	31.5 (31.8)	3.5 (3.4)	26.8 (26.5)	17.6 (17.9)	68.5 (67.9)	4.4	16 501	—	—
CoL _{1.2} Cl ₂	Yellowish green	14.9 (14.7)	31.3 (31.6)	3.0 (3.4)	26.0 (26.4)	17.4 (17.8)	67.8 (67.4)	3.4	9 705	1 011	0.9
NiL _{1.2} Cl ₂	Yellowish green	14.2 (14.7)	31.6 (31.6)	3.2 (3.3)	26.4 (26.4)	17.4 (17.8)	66.4 (67.4)	2.7	8 333	850	0.78
CuL _{1.2} Cl ₂	Green	15.4 (15.7)	31.4 (31.2)	3.6 (3.4)	25.7 (26.0)	17.3 (17.3)	67.0 (66.6)	1.6	14 492	—	—

free ligand peak at 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=NH) of the guanidinyll moiety showed negative shift by 10–20 cm⁻¹ in the Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes. This suggested its participation in coordination⁷. The non-participation of NH₂ group in coordination was further confirmed by non-shifting of the free ligand peak for δ_{NH_2} at 1 600–1 580 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. Medium to weak peaks observed for the free ligand at 1 000, 680 and 540 cm⁻¹ were assigned to pyridyl group vibrations. These shifted to 1 020, 690 and 540 cm⁻¹ respectively^{8,9} in Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. This suggests the coordination of pyridyl nitrogen with metal ions in the above complexes^{9,10}. In the Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes these bands remained unaltered. Additional weak bands observed at 540–580 and 440–470 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of complexes were assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ respectively^{10,11}.

Thermal studies : Thermograms of the complexes showed that the mode of decomposition of all the complexes are similar to each other. There is no weight loss upto 200° indicating the absence of coordinated water. Quantitative calculations of coordinated water molecules using literature method¹² also agreed well with this observation. Gradual loss in weight in the range 200–620° was a common TG feature of all the complexes due to oxidation of organic moiety. This oxidation was further reflected in DTA curves of each complexes. Quantitative estimation on the basis of TG curve also indicated the complete loss of ligand part (Table 1).

Thermal stability of these complexes fall in the order : Cu > Co > Mn > Ni > Fe.

Electronic spectra : Electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes exhibited single band at 14 814 and 16 501 cm⁻¹ which may be ascribed to ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g} and ⁶T_{2g}→⁶E_g transitions respectively, in an octahedral field¹³. In the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex, three well-resolved bands are observed at 8 298, 15 873 and 16 393 cm⁻¹ attributed to ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{2g} (ν_1), ⁴T_{1g}→⁴A_{2g} (ν_2) and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g} (P) (ν_3) transitions respectively¹⁴. The Ni^{II} complex showed two bands at 8 333 and 11 764 cm⁻¹ and are assigned to ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g} (ν_1) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g} (ν_2) respectively. The ν_3 band may be masked with

more intense charge transfer band¹⁵. The Cu^{II} complex showed a broad asymmetric ligand field band at 14 492 cm⁻¹ characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry¹¹, assigned to ³E_g→²T_{2g} transition. The value of 10 Dq, B' and β (Table 1) for the Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were calculated¹⁶.

Photoacoustic spectra : Photoacoustic spectra of the complexes showed two types of transitions, one in the lower wave length region and the other in higher region assigned to C-T and d-d bands respectively. The spectral pattern and magnitude of frequency of transitions are very similar to that obtained by electronic spectra and support the above geometry on the basis of earlier reported PAS data of similar systems¹⁷.

Esr spectra : Powder esr spectra of the Cu^{II} complex at liquid nitrogen temperature and at room temperature showed a broad peak giving $g_{\parallel}=2.31$ and $g_{\perp}=2.11$, i.e. $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. The spectral pattern is found to be quite similar to that of other copper complexes reported earlier^{16,18}. The $g_{\parallel}$ and $g_{\perp}$ values were also found to lie in similar range and the above molecule has axial symmetry.

Magnetic measurements : The observed magnetic moments of the complexes at room temperature (Table 1) lie in the range of high-spin octahedral complexes^{6,16}. However, slight lower value of magnetic moments of these complexes suggested super exchange interaction arising from bridging structure of these complexes¹⁶.

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Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes with Imidazole, Benzimidazole and Substituted Benzimidazoles

A. K. SINHA, (Mrs.) URMILA KUMARI, C. P. SINGH and

L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University,
Patna-800 005

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In previous communications, we reported the complexes of various transition metal ions with benzimidazole and substituted benzimidazoles¹⁻⁷ as well as oxovanadium(IV) complexes with some substituted benzimidazoles⁸. A non-detailed information on oxovanadium(IV) complexes [VO(BzH)₄·(H₂O)]SO₄ and [VO(Bz)₂] is also available⁹. In the present paper we report the preparation and characterisation of VO^{II} complexes with imidazole, benzimidazole and some substituted benzimidazoles.

Experimental

Benzimidazole, 2-methylbenzimidazole and 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole were prepared by reported method¹⁻³. Imidazole and oxovanadium(IV) salts (B.D.H.) were used. 90% ethanol was used for preparation of complexes.

Preparation of complexes: An ethanolic solution of hydrated oxovanadium(IV) salt (0.01 mol in 50 ml 90% ethanol) and a slight excess of ethanolic solution of the appropriate ligands (30–40 ml) were mixed together and refluxed on a steam-bath for 0.5 h when sulphato complexes separated out gradually. The complex chlorides were obtained on concentrating the refluxate to 15–20 ml and cooling it overnight. The complexes, bromide and iodide, were obtained by adding an aqueous solution of potassium bromide/iodide to the resulting solution of the complex chloride and concentrating to half of its volume. The neutral inner complexes were obtained by raising pH of the refluxate to 7–8 by adding an aqueous solution of sodium acetate (2–3 g in 10 ml). The products were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried over CaCl₂.

The results of elemental analysis, magnetic moment values (at 304 K), reflectance and important ir spectral bands of the complexes are given in Table 1. Magnetic susceptibility, uv and ir spectra were recorded as reported earlier¹⁻³.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of the complexes and formula are given in Table 1. The sulphato complexes have poor solubility in ethanol, methanol and dioxan whereas the complex halides are fairly soluble in these solvents. The complexes, in general, are soluble in DMF. The DMF solutions of the complex halides and [VO(BzH)₃]SO₄ display electrical conductance value in the range of 105–136 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm² indicating the anion to be uncoordinated. The PBzH complexes as well as the sulphato complexes was found to be anhydrous below 120° indicating uncoordinated nature of water molecules. The complex chlorides VO(L)₂Cl₂·nH₂O (L=IzH, BzH or MBzH and n=2 or 3) usually retained one H₂O below 120° indicating that retained H₂O is bonded to VO^{II}. The bischelated complexes [VO(PBzH)₂SO₄].3H₂O, [VO(PBzH)₂]X₂·nH₂O (X=Cl, Br or I and n=2 or 3) and [VO(PBz)₂].3H₂O display magnetic moment value (1.71–1.74 B.M.) equal to spin-only value whereas other complexes display subnormal magnetic moment value (1.59–1.69 B.M.) indicating their dimeric or polymeric character¹⁰.

The electronic reflectance spectra of the complexes exhibited low energy band at 12 800–14 280 cm⁻¹ corresponding to b₂-e_g transition. The second band at 15 300–18 530 cm⁻¹ was assigned to b₂-b₁* transition (10 Dq)¹⁴. The high energy band at 23 500–26 500 cm⁻¹ was assigned to b₂-a₁* transition plus charge transfer absorption. The 10 Dq